

Intrinsic reference basis and geometric nonregularity of finite-dimensional density matrices

José J. Gil^{1, *}

¹*Independent Researcher, 29690 Casares Costa, Spain*[†]

(Dated: May 22, 2026)

Finite-dimensional density matrices contain structural information that is not exhausted by their spectra. This work develops a geometric framework in two parts. The first establishes the intrinsic reference basis (IRB), a real orthonormal frame canonically determined by the real symmetric part of the density matrix, whose basis states are called principal population-coherence states. In this frame the population content is diagonal and ordered, while the total imaginary cohesion, measured by the Frobenius norm of the antisymmetric block, is preserved. The second part defines geometric nonregularity as the excess cohesion that remains after the dominant pure component of the discriminating decomposition has been subtracted; regularity is recovered as the vanishing limit. The normalization is fixed by the maximally nonregular discriminants, which exhibit a sharp dimensional transition: in dimension three (qutrits and three-dimensional polarization states) the maximizer features a circular-plus-linear structure, whereas in dimensions four and higher it admits a doubly-coherent two-sector structure. In three dimensions the excess cohesion is moreover dual to an excess spin vector, providing directional information that scalar measures discard. The framework reconciles the scalar definition of nonregularity with a geometric, representation-intrinsic formulation that exposes physical content beyond the eigenvalues.

I. INTRODUCTION

The density matrix is commonly analyzed through its eigenvalues and spectral projectors. This spectral perspective is indispensable for quantifying purity, entropy, rank, and mixedness, but it does not exhaust the structural information contained in a represented Hermitian matrix. In particular, it does not distinguish in an intrinsic way the population-bearing real part of the matrix from the imaginary correlations that carry oriented coherence. The present work develops a geometric framework in which this separation is made explicit and then uses it to formulate a measure of nonregularity.

The first ingredient is the intrinsic reference basis (IRB). For every finite-dimensional density matrix ρ written in matrix form, the decomposition $\rho = S + iT$, with $S = \text{Re } \rho$ real symmetric and $T = \text{Im } \rho$ real antisymmetric, is unique. Diagonalizing S by a real orthogonal transformation gives an intrinsic Cartesian frame in which

$$\rho_O = A + iN, \quad (1)$$

where A is diagonal and ordered and N remains real antisymmetric. The basis states of this frame will be called principal population-coherence states (PPCS). Equivalently, they are intrinsic resolving states: they diagonalize the population-bearing part of the density matrix and resolve the imaginary coherences on the corresponding intrinsic real planes. They are not, in general, eigenstates of ρ ; their role is instead to provide the real orthonormal

frame in which populations and coherences are separated optimally.

This distinction is central. A full unitary diagonalization of ρ removes all off-diagonal coherence and returns only the spectral mixture. A general complex unitary change of representation may also redistribute populations, real correlations, and imaginary coherences, because it need not preserve the decomposition into real and imaginary parts. By contrast, the IRB is obtained by a real orthogonal transformation: it removes all real off-diagonal correlations while preserving the Frobenius norm of the imaginary antisymmetric part. The IRB therefore organizes the population information and, simultaneously, preserves the global imaginary-coherence weight (referred to below as cohesion); it does not transfer cohesion into the complex phases of the basis.

The second ingredient is the discriminating decomposition [1, 2], which separates ρ into a dominant pure component, a normalized discriminant component (whose nonregular content is the central object of this work), and an isotropic remainder. The concept of nonregularity was introduced originally for three-dimensional polarization states [3] and then generalized to n -dimensional density matrices [1]. It identifies states whose discriminant component is not real in the intrinsic representation. Regularity is the limiting case in one-to-one correspondence with a real discriminant component, whereas nonregularity is the presence of intrinsic imaginary cohesion in the discriminant. The original scalar degree P_N [1, 3] quantifies this property through the correlation-asymmetry structure of the discriminant, weighted by the discriminant's coefficient in the full state.

The present article develops a complementary geometric measure. Once the IRB has separated populations from coherences, one may ask how much of the total intrinsic cohesion of ρ is explained by the dominant pure

* ppgil@unizar.es

† ORCID: 0000-0003-1740-2244

component of the discriminating decomposition and how much remains in the discriminant. The scalar geometric measure of nonregularity $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ is precisely the normalized Frobenius distance between the imaginary-coherence content of ρ and the contribution carried by that dominant pure component. It therefore measures the excess cohesion associated with the discriminant. Unlike spectral invariants, it is designed to probe structural information that is lost when the density matrix is reduced to its eigenvalues alone.

This formulation has direct quantum-mechanical significance. For a qutrit or, more generally, for a qudit density matrix, the IRB provides a representation-intrinsic population-coherence resolution that complements eigenvalue-based purity, entropy, and generalized Bloch-vector descriptions [4–7]. The word “coherence” is used here in this representation-resolved sense, and should be distinguished from resource-theoretic coherence relative to an externally prescribed incoherent basis [8, 9]. In the present construction the resolving basis is not externally chosen: it is determined by ρ itself through its real part. The same mathematical object also describes three-component classical polarization matrices, where the three-dimensional case has a direct spin-vector interpretation.

The three-dimensional case is especially instructive. It is simultaneously the qutrit case, the first nontrivial member of the qudit hierarchy, and the case of genuine three-component polarization. Earlier work on sets of orthogonal three-dimensional polarization states showed that the spectral and characteristic decompositions are controlled by orthonormal complex three-dimensional Jones vectors whose mathematical orthogonality does not, in general, coincide with the orthogonality of their polarization-ellipse planes [10]. That analysis revealed physical structure not apparent from eigenvalues alone and pointed also to applications in three-level quantum systems and ternary quantum logic. The vector form of $P_{Ng}^{(3)}$ developed here continues that program: it resolves not only the magnitude of nonregularity but also the intrinsic direction of the excess spin, thereby distinguishing states that the scalar degree alone does not separate. In this sense the present work completes, on the quantitative side, the structural geometric analysis of orthogonal three-dimensional eigenstate sets developed in Ref. [10]: that work identified geometrical configurations and constraints; here those configurations acquire an intrinsic quantitative measure, and in three dimensions a vector refinement that resolves both magnitude and direction.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II first develops the IRB as a cohesion-preserving population-coherence representation and then recalls the indices of purity and the discriminating decomposition. Section III determines the maximally nonregular discriminant and the normalization constant in all dimensions, showing the structural transition between $n = 3$ and $n \geq 4$. Section IV defines the scalar geometric measure and proves its basic properties. Section V develops the vector formu-

lation for $n = 3$. Section VI compares P_{Ng} with the original scalar degree P_N . Section VII discusses the quantum-mechanical interpretation, the qutrit/polarization case, and the information that becomes visible only in the IRB formulation.

II. INTRINSIC REFERENCE BASIS AND DISCRIMINATING DECOMPOSITION

A. Density matrices, PPCS, and the IRB

An $n \times n$ density matrix ρ ($\rho = \rho^\dagger \geq 0$, $\text{tr} \rho = 1$) has ordered eigenvalues $\lambda_1 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_n \geq 0$ and spectral decomposition $\rho = \sum_k \lambda_k \hat{u}_k \hat{u}_k^\dagger$. Independently of this spectral representation, every Hermitian matrix has the unique real-imaginary decomposition

$$\rho = S + iT, \quad S = S^\top, \quad T = -T^\top, \quad (2)$$

with $S = \text{Re} \rho$ real symmetric and $T = \text{Im} \rho$ real anti-symmetric. Since S is real symmetric, it possesses a real orthonormal eigenbasis. The real orthogonal matrix Q_O whose columns are these eigenvectors defines the *intrinsic reference basis* (IRB), in agreement with the terminology used in previous work. In this basis

$$\rho_O = Q_O^\top \rho Q_O = A + iN, \quad (3)$$

where

$$A = Q_O^\top S Q_O = \text{diag}(a_1, \dots, a_n), \quad N = Q_O^\top T Q_O, \quad (4)$$

with $a_1 \geq \dots \geq a_n \geq 0$ and $\sum_k a_k = 1$. The numbers a_k are the intrinsic populations. They are not the eigenvalues of ρ in general; they are the eigenvalues of the population-bearing real part S .

The basis states forming the IRB will be called *principal population-coherence states* (PPCS). They may also be described as *intrinsic resolving states*. The adjective “principal” refers to the diagonalization of $S = \text{Re} \rho$, not to the spectral diagonalization of ρ . The PPCS are therefore not, in general, eigenstates of the full density matrix. Their function is different: they are the real orthonormal states that provide the Cartesian frame in which the intrinsic populations appear as ordered diagonal weights and the imaginary coherences are resolved in the anti-symmetric matrix N .

A structural feature implicit in this construction deserves emphasis. Because $S = \text{Re} \rho$ is real symmetric, its orthonormal eigenvectors can be chosen real with respect to the representation in which ρ is written; the PPCS components are then real numbers, defined up to the residual $O(n)$ freedom of eigenvectors of a real symmetric matrix (signs for nondegenerate eigenvalues, and real-orthogonal rotations within degenerate eigenspaces). In a complex Hilbert space, the real vectors of a given representation form a privileged real subspace whose physical content depends on the application: in polarization

theory they describe linearly polarized states, with no phase delay between Cartesian field components; in systems with a time-reversal operation implemented as complex conjugation in the chosen basis, they describe time-reversal-invariant states; in general, they are the states whose representation contains no imaginary content. The IRB is therefore canonically defined, for every density matrix written in any representation, as the unique real orthonormal basis (modulo the residual $O(n)$ freedom) in which the population structure is diagonal and ordered. The cohesion N measures the imaginary content of ρ relative to this maximally real basis. The geometric descriptors derived from N are accordingly well-defined, computable, real-orthogonal-intrinsic physical functionals of the represented density matrix. They are not invariant under arbitrary complex unitary changes of representation, and this is the intended behavior: in physical applications the representation itself carries content (a Cartesian spatial frame in polarimetry, an energy or computational basis in finite quantum systems, a basis aligned with time reversal in T -symmetric problems), and the descriptors are designed to keep that content rather than to average it away.

For the three-dimensional analyses developed in Sections V and VI we adopt the labeling $(X_O, Y_O, Z_O) \equiv (\hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2, \hat{e}_3)$, in agreement with the conventions of Refs. [11, 12, 14]. With this assignment the population ordering reads $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq a_3$, the dominant ellipse lies in the $X_O Y_O$ plane, and Z_O is the axis perpendicular to that plane, identified below as the spin axis of any regular three-dimensional state.

This gives the IRB a precise optimality property. Among all bases related by real orthogonal transformations, the IRB makes the real off-diagonal part vanish:

$$\text{offdiag}(\text{Re } \rho_O) = 0. \quad (5)$$

All non-diagonal structure that remains in ρ_O is therefore carried by iN .

B. Cohesion-preserving character of the IRB

The same orthogonal transformation that diagonalizes S transforms the imaginary part via congruence, $T \mapsto N = Q_O^T T Q_O$. Therefore

$$\|N\|_F = \|T\|_F. \quad (6)$$

We shall refer to this Frobenius weight of the imaginary antisymmetric part as the total intrinsic cohesion, or simply cohesion when no ambiguity arises. Equation (6) shows that the IRB is not a representation that suppresses coherence. Rather, it diagonalizes and orders the population structure while preserving the global imaginary-coherence weight. The cohesion that appears in N is the intrinsic imaginary coherence between the real directions defined by the PPCS.

Degeneracies of S produce the natural residual orthogonal freedom inside the degenerate subspaces. This is

analogous to the residual freedom of spectral eigenvectors in a degenerate eigenspace. Intrinsic populations are then unchanged, while the corresponding coherence subblocks transform covariantly inside the degenerate subspaces. Scalar quantities constructed from Frobenius norms remain invariant under that residual freedom; vector or directional quantities are understood modulo the same residual orthogonal transformations.

The covariance relevant for the geometric quantities introduced below is therefore covariance under real orthogonal changes of frame,

$$\rho \mapsto Q_O^T \rho Q_O, \quad Q_O \in O(n), \quad (7)$$

or under $SO(n)$ when orientation is fixed. Under such transformations S and T transform separately, and the Frobenius norms of their intrinsic parts are preserved. The discriminating decomposition is unitary covariant and its weights are spectral invariants, but a general complex unitary transformation need not preserve the real-imaginary split (2). The IRB descriptors are therefore representation-intrinsic real-orthogonal invariants, designed to keep the population axes determined by S distinct from the cohesion encoded in T and, in the IRB, in N [1, 16].

The IRB-based decomposition $\rho_O = A + iN$ underlies independently developed geometric representations in different communities: the polarization density object of Ref. [11], in which the diagonal entries of A form the semi-axes of an intrinsic ellipsoid decorated by the spin density vector dual to N ; the geometric interpretation of the three-dimensional coherence matrix for nonparaxial polarization developed by Dennis [13]; and the qutrit visualization of Kurzynski et al. [17], in which the diagonalization of $\text{Re } \rho$ defines a metric ellipsoid decorated by a spin-1 polarization vector. Both representations rely, explicitly or implicitly, on the same real-orthogonal eigendecomposition that defines the IRB, and both decorate it with a vectorial object whose direction encodes the imaginary content of the state. The fact that two communities (three-dimensional polarization optics and quantum-information theory of qutrits) have arrived at the same real-orthogonal decomposition by independent routes is a strong indication of its representation-theoretic naturalness. The present work provides the quantitative measure of nonregularity that this decomposition makes geometrically transparent in both contexts.

For $n = 3$, the antisymmetric N is dual to the spin vector $\mathbf{n} = (n_1, n_2, n_3)$ via $N_{ij} = -\frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_{ijk}n_k$, equivalently $n_k = -\varepsilon_{ijk}N_{ij}$ [14, 15].¹ For any pure state in dimension

¹ We adopt the convention of Refs. [14, 15], where \mathbf{n} is a dimensionless polarimetric quantity dual to the antisymmetric part of the coherence matrix. In monochromatic fields, \mathbf{n} is proportional to the electric spin angular momentum density vector; for random polychromatic fields, however, the two vectors are not in general parallel, as shown in Ref. [15].

n , the IRB reduces to a 2×2 active block with a single free parameter, the ellipticity angle $\chi \in [-\pi/4, \pi/4]$, defined so that $M_1 = |\cos 2\chi|$ and the coherence norm equals $|\sin 2\chi|$. In the polarization realization $\chi = 0$ corresponds to a linearly polarized pure state and $\chi = \pm\pi/4$ to circular polarization; in the qudit realization it corresponds to a real state and to a balanced two-level superposition with relative phase $\pm\pi/2$, respectively.

The antisymmetric block N admits a hierarchical refinement, obtained by normalizing its entries by the geometric means of the corresponding intrinsic populations; the resulting dimensionless object is a real antisymmetric matrix whose skew-singular values are bounded above by unity and which generalizes the metaspin vector of three-dimensional polarization theory to arbitrary dimension. The full development of this refinement, together with the explicit construction in the full-rank and rank-deficient cases, will be reported elsewhere. The present work uses the IRB and the discriminating decomposition to formulate the scalar and vector geometric measures of nonregularity.

C. Indices of purity and discriminating decomposition

The $n - 1$ indices of purity of ρ [18],

$$P_k = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i - k\lambda_{k+1}, \quad k = 1, \dots, n-1, \quad (8)$$

satisfy $0 \leq P_1 \leq \dots \leq P_{n-1} \leq 1$. We introduce the shorthand notation

$$w := P_{n-1} - P_1 \geq 0 \quad (9)$$

for the discriminant weight, used throughout to lighten intermediate expressions. The *discriminating decomposition* [1] is

$$\rho = P_1 \rho_p + (P_{n-1} - P_1) \rho_d + (1 - P_{n-1}) \frac{I_n}{n}, \quad (10)$$

where $\rho_p = \hat{u}_1 \hat{u}_1^\dagger$, ρ_d is the normalized *discriminant component*, and I_n is the identity. A state is *regular* if and only if the discriminant component is real in the intrinsic representation, equivalently $\text{Im}(\rho_d) = 0$ [1, 3]. Thus regularity is not merely the small-nonregularity regime; it is the limiting case in one-to-one correspondence with the absence of cohesion in the discriminant.

The discriminant component shares its eigenvectors with ρ (by construction of (10)) and its eigenvalues are

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_1 = \mu_2 &= \frac{\lambda_2 - \lambda_n}{w}, \\ \mu_k &= \frac{\lambda_k - \lambda_n}{w}, \quad k = 3, \dots, n-1, \\ \mu_n &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

with $w := P_{n-1} - P_1$, where the middle range is absent for $n = 3$. Two structural facts follow immediately: the two largest eigenvalues of ρ_d are always equal ($\mu_1 = \mu_2$), and $\mu_n = 0$ (the discriminant is rank-deficient).

The equality $\mu_1 = \mu_2$ admits the following derivation. For $k \geq 2$, the eigenvectors \hat{u}_k of ρ are orthogonal to \hat{u}_1 , so $\rho_p = \hat{u}_1 \hat{u}_1^\dagger$ contributes zero to their eigenvalues; the fully mixed component I_n/n contributes $(1 - P_{n-1})/n$ uniformly. Hence $\lambda_k = w\mu_k + (1 - P_{n-1})/n$ for $k \geq 2$. Setting $k = n$ and using $\mu_n = 0$ gives $\lambda_n = (1 - P_{n-1})/n$, so $\mu_k = (\lambda_k - \lambda_n)/w$ for $k = 2, \dots, n-1$. For $k = 1$ one has $\lambda_1 = P_1 + w\mu_1 + (1 - P_{n-1})/n$; using $P_1 = \lambda_1 - \lambda_2$ then gives $\lambda_2 = w\mu_1 + (1 - P_{n-1})/n$, and therefore $\mu_1 = (\lambda_2 - \lambda_n)/w = \mu_2$.

D. Dimensional hierarchy of the decomposition

For $n = 1$ and $n = 2$, the decomposition (10) has no discriminant component. For $n = 1$ the state is pure, so the only component is ρ_p . For $n = 2$ there is a single index of purity, P_1 , with $P_{n-1} = P_1$ and therefore $w = 0$ identically; the decomposition reduces to $\rho = P_1 \rho_p + (1 - P_1) I_2/2$. The dimension $n = 3$ is therefore the minimal one in which a nonzero discriminant component can appear and nonregularity can arise, with consequences for the structure of the perfect nonregular state analyzed in the next section.

E. Original scalar degree of nonregularity

The scalar degree [1, 3] may be written in the form

$$P_N = (P_{n-1} - P_1) P_N(\rho_d), \quad (12)$$

where $P_N(\rho_d)$ is the degree of nonregularity of the normalized discriminant. In the three-dimensional case this degree has the closed expression

$$P_N(\rho_d) = 4\hat{m}_{d3}, \quad (13)$$

where \hat{m}_{d3} denotes the smallest intrinsic population of ρ_d (i.e., the smallest eigenvalue of $\text{Re } \rho_d$). In arbitrary dimension the original definition is formulated through the correlation-asymmetry properties of the discriminant [1]; Eq. (13) is therefore used below only in the three-dimensional comparison, where it is the standard closed form. The scalar degree satisfies $P_N \in [0, 1]$, vanishes if and only if ρ is regular, and reaches unity for the corresponding perfect nonregular states.

III. DIMENSIONAL STRUCTURE OF MAXIMUM NONREGULARITY

A. A conjugate-subspace bound

The normalization of the geometric measure of nonregularity is fixed by the largest possible imaginary content

of a normalized discriminant. Let ρ_d be a discriminant state, with eigenvalues $\mu_1 \geq \dots \geq \mu_n$ satisfying the structural conditions derived in Sec. II, namely

$$\mu_1 = \mu_2, \quad \mu_n = 0, \quad \sum_{k=1}^n \mu_k = 1. \quad (14)$$

Write $\rho_d = S_d + iT_d$, with $S_d = \text{Re } \rho_d$ real symmetric and $T_d = \text{Im } \rho_d$ real antisymmetric. Since ρ_d is Hermitian,

$$\|T_d\|_F^2 = \frac{1}{2} [\text{tr}(\rho_d^2) - \text{tr}(\rho_d \bar{\rho}_d)], \quad (15)$$

where the bar denotes entrywise complex conjugation. This identity is basis independent under real orthogonal changes of reference frame and makes explicit that the imaginary part measures how far ρ_d is from its complex conjugate.

The spectral part of (15) gives the first universal bound. If $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = m$, then because $\mu_1 \geq \dots \geq \mu_n \geq 0$ every eigenvalue lies in $[0, m]$, and therefore

$$\text{tr}(\rho_d^2) = \sum_{k=1}^n \mu_k^2 \leq m \sum_{k=1}^n \mu_k = m \leq \frac{1}{2}, \quad (16)$$

where the last inequality follows from $\mu_1 + \mu_2 = 2m \leq \sum_k \mu_k = 1$. Consequently,

$$\|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F^2 \leq \frac{1}{4}, \quad (17)$$

with equality possible only when the spectrum of ρ_d is $(1/2, 1/2, 0, \dots, 0)$ and $\text{tr}(\rho_d \bar{\rho}_d) = 0$. Thus, in all dimensions, a maximizer of the spectral part of the bound is one half of a rank-two projector,

$$\rho_d = \frac{1}{2}P, \quad P^2 = P = P^\dagger, \quad \text{rank } P = 2. \quad (18)$$

The additional condition $\text{tr}(P\bar{P}) = 0$ that saturates the bound is attainable only for $n \geq 4$; in dimension three it is obstructed by the unavoidable intersection between a two-dimensional support subspace and its complex conjugate, analyzed below.

Let $\mathcal{S} = \text{Ran } P$ and $\bar{\mathcal{S}} = \text{Ran } \bar{P}$ be the support of P and its complex conjugate. The positive quantity $\text{tr}(P\bar{P})$ is the squared Hilbert-Schmidt overlap between these two rank-two subspaces; equivalently, it equals the sum of the squared cosines of the principal (canonical) angles between them. Since $\rho_d = P/2$, Eq. (15) becomes

$$\|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F^2 = \frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{8} \text{tr}(P\bar{P}). \quad (19)$$

The maximization of imaginary content is therefore reduced to minimizing the overlap between a two-dimensional complex subspace and its conjugate.

B. The $n = 3$ case: a forced real direction

In dimension three, two complex two-dimensional subspaces of \mathbb{C}^3 must intersect nontrivially, since

$$\dim(\mathcal{S} \cap \bar{\mathcal{S}}) = \dim \mathcal{S} + \dim \bar{\mathcal{S}} - \dim(\mathcal{S} + \bar{\mathcal{S}}) \geq 2 + 2 - 3 = 1. \quad (20)$$

Since $\mathcal{S} \cap \bar{\mathcal{S}} \neq \{0\}$, at least one principal angle between the two rank-two subspaces is zero, so one of the two squared cosines of principal angles contributes unity to $\text{tr}(P\bar{P})$, giving $\text{tr}(P\bar{P}) \geq 1$. Equation (19) then yields

$$\|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F^2 \leq \frac{1}{8}, \quad \|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F \leq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}. \quad (21)$$

The bound is sharp. Equality occurs when the intersection $\mathcal{S} \cap \bar{\mathcal{S}}$ is exactly one-dimensional and real, while the remaining one-dimensional directions in \mathcal{S} and $\bar{\mathcal{S}}$ are mutually orthogonal. Choosing the real common direction as the first intrinsic axis and the orthogonal real plane as the $(2, 3)$ plane gives

$$\rho_d^{\text{max},3} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{4} & -\frac{i}{4} \\ 0 & \frac{i}{4} & \frac{1}{4} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

This state is one half of the projector onto the subspace spanned by a real basis vector and by a maximally coherent two-level state in the orthogonal real plane. In polarization language it is an equiprobable mixture of a linearly polarized pure state and a circularly polarized pure state. In qutrit language it is an equiprobable mixture of a real basis state and a balanced superposition of the other two levels with relative phase $\pm\pi/2$. Its imaginary norm is

$$\mathcal{N}_3 = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}. \quad (23)$$

Thus the special character of three dimensions is not a convention: it is forced by the unavoidable one-dimensional overlap between any rank-two support subspace and its conjugate.

C. The $n \geq 4$ case: a conjugate-orthogonal support

For $n \geq 4$, a two-dimensional complex subspace can be orthogonal to its conjugate. Taking, for instance,

$$\mathcal{S} = \text{span} \left\{ \frac{\hat{e}_1 - i\hat{e}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\hat{e}_3 - i\hat{e}_4}{\sqrt{2}} \right\}, \quad (24)$$

we have $\mathcal{S} \perp \bar{\mathcal{S}}$, so that $\text{tr}(P\bar{P}) = 0$. The universal bound (17) is therefore saturated, and

$$\mathcal{N}_{n \geq 4} = \frac{1}{2}. \quad (25)$$

In the corresponding intrinsic representation,

$$\rho_d^{\max,n} = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & i & 0 & 0 & \cdots \\ -i & 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & i & \cdots \\ 0 & 0 & -i & 1 & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots \end{pmatrix}, \quad (26)$$

with all remaining dimensions carrying zero population. This is an equiprobable incoherent mixture of two mutually orthogonal maximally coherent two-level pure states. In the language of qudits, the support splits into two disjoint two-level sectors, each carrying a balanced relative phase $\pm\pi/2$; in the language of polarization-type systems, it is the doubly-circular configuration.

Theorem 1 (Perfect nonregular discriminants). *The maximum of $\|\text{Im}(\rho_d)\|_F$ over all normalized discriminating states is*

$$\mathcal{N}_n = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} & n = 3, \\ \frac{1}{2} & n \geq 4, \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

achieved by $\rho_d^{\max,3}$ in Eq. (22) for $n = 3$ and by $\rho_d^{\max,n}$ in Eq. (26) for $n \geq 4$, up to real orthogonal equivalence and handedness conventions. The perfect nonregular state in dimension n is the corresponding normalized discriminant itself, i.e., $\rho = \rho_d^{\max,n}$ with $P_1 = 0$ and $P_{n-1} = 1$.

Proof. Equation (16) gives $\text{tr}(\rho_d^2) \leq 1/2$ for every discriminating state. Together with (15), this gives the universal upper bound $\|\text{Im} \rho_d\|_F \leq 1/2$. For $n \geq 4$ this bound is attained by the rank-two projector whose support is conjugate-orthogonal to its complex conjugate, Eq. (24), giving Eq. (26). For $n = 3$, the support of any rank-two projector necessarily intersects its conjugate in at least one dimension, which implies $\text{tr}(P\bar{P}) \geq 1$ and hence $\|\text{Im} \rho_d\|_F \leq 1/(2\sqrt{2})$ by (19). The bound is attained exactly when the intersection is a real line and the remaining pair of conjugate directions is mutually orthogonal, yielding Eq. (22). Direct verification for the constructed maximizers proceeds as follows. For Eq. (26) with $n \geq 4$, the corresponding rank-two projector $P = 2\rho_d^{\max,n}$ satisfies $P\bar{P} = 0$ blockwise, since each 2×2 block factor obeys $(1/2)(1, i; -i, 1) \cdot (1/2)(1, -i; i, 1) = 0$; hence $\text{tr}(P\bar{P}) = 0$ and Eq. (19) gives $\|\text{Im} \rho_d^{\max,n}\|_F^2 = 1/4$. For Eq. (22) with $n = 3$, $P = 2\rho_d^{\max,3} = \text{diag}(1, 0, 0) + P_2$, where P_2 projects onto $(|1\rangle - i|2\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$, and direct evaluation yields $\text{tr}(P\bar{P}) = 1$, attaining the lower bound forced by the dimensional obstruction and giving $\|\text{Im} \rho_d^{\max,3}\|_F^2 = 1/8$. The equality conditions characterize the maximizer up to the residual freedoms: in $n = 3$, an $O(2)$ rotation in the plane orthogonal to the real intersection and the choice of handedness of the circular component; in $n \geq 4$, a permutation of the two coherent two-level sectors, an $O(2)$ rotation in each, the handedness of each, and an arbitrary real orthogonal transformation acting on the $n - 4$ trivial directions. \square

D. Comparison and physical significance of the two regimes

Table I summarizes the dimensional structure.

The transition from $n = 3$ to $n = 4$ is a genuine structural transition. In $n = 3$, the two-dimensional support of the discriminant is forced to share one real direction with its conjugate, so the perfect nonregular state necessarily contains a real one-dimensional component. Starting from $n = 4$, the support can be conjugate-orthogonal to its conjugate, and the perfect nonregular state becomes a more symmetric pair of independent maximally coherent two-level sectors. For $n \geq 5$, including all odd dimensions, the same doubly-coherent object is simply embedded in the larger Hilbert space, with the extra dimensions carrying zero population. The transition is therefore independent of parity: it depends only on whether $n \geq 4$, the threshold at which a conjugate-orthogonal two-dimensional support fits inside \mathbb{C}^n .

This result also clarifies the scope of the perfect nonregular configuration discussed in Ref. [1]. That configuration should be understood as a particular construction within the framework of that work, not as a general dimensional maximizer. The maximization carried out here yields the dimension-dependent general form: the three-dimensional maximizer is necessarily circular-plus-linear, whereas in all dimensions four and higher the maximizer is the conjugate-orthogonal two-sector state. We will refer to \mathcal{N}_n as the *maximum discriminant cohesion*; it provides the natural normalization of the geometric measure introduced in the next section.

The ratio $\mathcal{N}_{n \geq 4}/\mathcal{N}_3 = \sqrt{2}$ quantifies the gain in maximum intrinsic cohesion when a second mutually orthogonal maximally coherent sector becomes available. In quantum mechanics this distinction separates the qutrit case, where the support-subspace geometry imposes a real direction, from higher-dimensional qudits, where the maximally nonregular discriminant can be realized by two conjugate-orthogonal two-level sectors. In three-component polarization the same dimensional obstruction explains why the perfect nonregular state has the familiar circular-plus-linear form rather than a doubly-circular one.

E. Saturation pattern of the metaspin tensor of the discriminant

The maximizers identified in Theorem 1 admit a transparent reformulation in terms of the skew-singular values of a normalized antisymmetric tensor associated with the discriminant, whose dimensionless magnitudes are bounded by unity. In dimension three, this tensor has a single nonzero magnitude that saturates the bound, in correspondence with the circular-plus-linear structure of the maximizer. In dimensions four and higher, two such magnitudes saturate simultaneously, in correspondence with the doubly-coherent two-sector structure. In

TABLE I. ...

n	\mathcal{N}_n	Perfect nonregular state
1, 2	—	No discriminant component; nonregularity absent
3	$\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}$	Real direction plus a coherent two-level sector
≥ 4	$\frac{1}{2}$	Two mutually orthogonal coherent two-level sectors

both maximizing discriminants the active pair weights $a_i^d a_j^d$ are equal in the relevant blocks (1/16 in $n = 3$ and again 1/16 for both blocks in $n \geq 4$); the increase from one to two simultaneously saturated pairs therefore multiplies the squared cohesion by two, and the ratio $\mathcal{N}_{n \geq 4}/\mathcal{N}_3 = \sqrt{2}$ is identified with the square root of the number of simultaneously saturating pairs, a structural quantity rather than a numerical coincidence.

For $n \geq 5$ a richer set of discriminating configurations is admissible. Beyond the two simultaneously saturating values of the doubly-coherent configuration, single-pair dominated states with one saturating value and a partial second one are admissible, as are multiply-coherent configurations involving up to $\lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ pairs. All such configurations are subject to the same dimensional upper bound \mathcal{N}_n on the Frobenius norm of $\text{Im } \rho_d$, but only the doubly-saturated two-sector configuration attains it; the remaining configurations sit strictly below. A full hierarchical analysis distinguishing these submaximal configurations by the distribution of their normalized magnitudes will be developed separately. The scalar formulation of the present article is the global magnitude that such a hierarchy refines into level-by-level contributions.

IV. THE SCALAR GEOMETRIC MEASURE

A. Decomposition of the excess cohesion

Taking the imaginary part of the discriminating decomposition (10) gives

$$\text{Im}(\rho) - P_1 \text{Im}(\rho_p) = (P_{n-1} - P_1) \text{Im}(\rho_d). \quad (28)$$

The left-hand side is the imaginary-coherence content of ρ after subtracting the contribution carried by the dominant pure component. We call this antisymmetric matrix the *excess cohesion* of ρ ,

$$\Delta_N(\rho) := \text{Im}(\rho) - P_1 \text{Im}(\rho_p) = (P_{n-1} - P_1) \text{Im}(\rho_d). \quad (29)$$

Its Frobenius norm is the distance, in the real vector space of antisymmetric matrices, between the intrinsic cohesion of the full density matrix and the cohesion attributable to the dominant pure component. Equation (28) shows that this distance is precisely the cohesion carried by the discriminant, multiplied by its structural weight.

Definition 1. *The scalar geometric measure of nonreg-*

ularity of ρ is the normalized excess-cohesion norm

$$P_{Ng}^{(n)} := \frac{(P_{n-1} - P_1) \|\text{Im}(\rho_d)\|_F}{\mathcal{N}_n} = \frac{\|\text{Im}(\rho) - P_1 \text{Im}(\rho_p)\|_F}{\mathcal{N}_n}, \quad (30)$$

with \mathcal{N}_n given by (27). Explicitly,

$$P_{Ng}^{(n)} = \begin{cases} 2\sqrt{2}(P_2 - P_1) \|\text{Im}(\rho_d)\|_F & n = 3, \\ 2(P_{n-1} - P_1) \|\text{Im}(\rho_d)\|_F & n \geq 4. \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

The two values of the normalization constant \mathcal{N}_n reflect the dimensional character of the perfect nonregular state itself, not two distinct maxima of $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$. The definition makes the one-to-one regular/nonregular boundary explicit: $P_{Ng}^{(n)} = 0$ exactly when the discriminant contributes no imaginary cohesion. The measure remains bounded by unity in every dimension and reaches unity uniquely at the perfect nonregular state of that dimension, as stated in Theorem 2 below.

Theorem 2. *The scalar geometric measure $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ takes values in $[0, 1]$, vanishes if and only if ρ is regular, equals unity if and only if ρ is the perfect nonregular state for its dimension, and is invariant under real orthogonal transformations of the represented matrix.*

Proof. The bound $P_{Ng}^{(n)} \leq 1$ follows from Theorem 1, which gives $\|\text{Im}(\rho_d)\|_F \leq \mathcal{N}_n$, combined with $P_{n-1} - P_1 \leq 1$. The equivalence $P_{Ng}^{(n)} = 0 \iff \rho$ regular follows from the factored form (30): the product vanishes if and only if either $P_{n-1} = P_1$ (in which case there is no discriminant component, and ρ is regular by definition) or $\text{Im}(\rho_d) = 0$ (the discriminant is real, which is precisely the definition of regularity [1]). The equality $P_{Ng}^{(n)} = 1$ requires simultaneously $P_{n-1} - P_1 = 1$, so $\rho = \rho_d$, and $\|\text{Im}(\rho_d)\|_F = \mathcal{N}_n$, which by Theorem 1 uniquely characterizes the perfect nonregular state. Finally, under $\rho \mapsto Q_O^\top \rho Q_O$ with Q_O real orthogonal, the discriminating decomposition transforms covariantly, $\rho_p \mapsto Q_O^\top \rho_p Q_O$ and $\rho_d \mapsto Q_O^\top \rho_d Q_O$, while P_1 and P_{n-1} are unchanged because they are spectral weights. Moreover, $\text{Im}(Q_O^\top X Q_O) = Q_O^\top \text{Im}(X) Q_O$ for every Hermitian X , and the Frobenius norm is invariant under real orthogonal congruence. Hence the excess-cohesion norm in (30) is a real-orthogonal intrinsic invariant. \square

B. Scope of the scalar measure and its hierarchical refinement

By construction, $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ is the Frobenius norm of the excess cohesion normalized by the maximum-discriminant-cohesion constant of the corresponding dimension. As a single scalar, it does not resolve how the excess cohesion is distributed across the intrinsic principal pairs of the discriminant. In three dimensions this limitation is overcome by the vector formulation developed in Sec. V, which exploits Hodge duality to recover the intrinsic direction of the excess cohesion. In dimensions four and higher, Hodge duality is no longer available, and the appropriate refinement is hierarchical rather than vectorial: the antisymmetric matrix $\text{Im } \rho_d$ admits a nested family of dimensionless invariants constructed from the skew-singular values of an associated normalized tensor. The construction and properties of this hierarchical refinement will be developed separately. The relation to the present measure is direct: $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ is the global magnitude that such a hierarchy refines into level-by-level contributions, in the same sense in which the scalar degree of purity refines into the indices of purity. The two formulations are complementary, scalar magnitude on one side and hierarchical distribution on the other.

V. VECTOR FORMULATION IN THREE DIMENSIONS

A. The vector measure of nonregularity

In three dimensions the antisymmetric 3×3 matrix N is dual to the spin vector \mathbf{n} via $N_{ij} = -\frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_{ijk}n_k$, equivalently $n_k = -\varepsilon_{ijk}N_{ij}$ [14, 15]. This duality promotes the excess cohesion, which in arbitrary dimension is an antisymmetric matrix, to a genuinely vector object for $n = 3$.

Definition 2. *The vector geometric measure of nonregularity of a three-dimensional density matrix ρ is*

$$\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)} := 2(\mathbf{n} - P_1\mathbf{n}_p) = 2\boldsymbol{\delta}, \quad (32)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the spin vector of ρ , \mathbf{n}_p is the spin vector of the dominant pure component ρ_p , and $\boldsymbol{\delta} := \mathbf{n} - P_1\mathbf{n}_p$ is the excess spin vector, both spin vectors being evaluated in the IRB of ρ .

The scalar measure of Sec. IV is recovered as the norm of the vector,

$$P_{Ng}^{(3)} = |\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}| = 2|\boldsymbol{\delta}|, \quad (33)$$

so that the vector measure is a strict refinement of the scalar one. The equivalence between (33) and the general definition (30) is a consequence of the $n = 3$ Frobenius identity $\|N\|_F = |\mathbf{n}|/\sqrt{2}$ for antisymmetric 3×3 matrices dual to three-component vectors via $N_{ij} = -\frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_{ijk}n_k$.

Proposition 1. *The vector measure $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ satisfies: $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)} = \mathbf{0}$ if and only if ρ is regular; $|\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}| \leq 1$, with equality if and only if ρ is the perfect nonregular state of dimension three; the norm is invariant under real orthogonal transformations of the represented matrix; and the direction of $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ in the IRB of ρ is a structural property of the state, up to the residual freedom associated with degenerate intrinsic populations.*

Proof. The first three statements follow from the corresponding properties of the scalar measure (Theorem 2) via (33). The last follows from the definition: once the IRB of ρ has been fixed, both \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{n}_p are defined in that basis. If $\text{Re } \rho$ has degenerate eigenvalues, the direction is understood modulo the corresponding residual real orthogonal freedom within the degenerate subspace. \square

B. Three distinct spin vectors and three equivalent regularity criteria

Three distinct objects coexist in the same spin space (see Fig. 1): the total spin \mathbf{n} of the full state ρ , in the IRB of ρ ; the spin contribution $P_1\mathbf{n}_p$ of the dominant pure component, in the same IRB; and the excess spin $\boldsymbol{\delta} = \mathbf{n} - P_1\mathbf{n}_p$. The regularity criterion of Ref. [11] states that ρ is regular if and only if $n_1 = n_2 = 0$ in its IRB, i.e., the total spin satisfies $\mathbf{n} \parallel Z_O$. The new measure is based on the excess spin $\boldsymbol{\delta}$, not the total spin. The three statements

$$\rho \text{ regular} \iff \mathbf{n} \parallel Z_O \iff \boldsymbol{\delta} = \mathbf{0} \quad (34)$$

are nevertheless exactly equivalent. The first equivalence is the criterion of Ref. [11]. The second proceeds as follows. Assume first that ρ has a nontrivial discriminant ($w := P_2 - P_1 > 0$). If ρ is regular then $\text{Im}(\rho_d) = 0$; hence $\mathbf{n}_d = \mathbf{0}$ and $\boldsymbol{\delta} = w\mathbf{n}_d = \mathbf{0}$. Conversely, if $\boldsymbol{\delta} = \mathbf{0}$ then $w\mathbf{n}_d = \mathbf{0}$, which since $w > 0$ forces $\mathbf{n}_d = \mathbf{0}$. In three dimensions the discriminant ρ_d has a single off-diagonal antisymmetric pair in its own IRB, dual to \mathbf{n}_d ; therefore $\mathbf{n}_d = \mathbf{0}$ implies $\text{Im}(\rho_d) = 0$, so ρ is regular. The case $w = 0$ is automatic: the decomposition (10) then has no discriminant component, ρ is regular by definition, and $\boldsymbol{\delta} = \mathbf{0}$ trivially.

C. Decomposition of the excess spin

Decompose the excess spin in the IRB of ρ as

$$\boldsymbol{\delta} = \underbrace{(\delta_1, \delta_2, 0)}_{\boldsymbol{\delta}_{NR}} + \underbrace{(0, 0, \delta_3)}_{\boldsymbol{\delta}_R}, \quad (35)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{NR}$ is the transverse component in the dominant X_OY_O plane and $\boldsymbol{\delta}_R$ is the axial component along Z_O . Three representative cases illustrate this decomposition (Fig. 1). For a regular state, $\mathbf{n} \parallel Z_O$ and $P_1\mathbf{n}_p = \mathbf{n}$, so that $\boldsymbol{\delta} = \mathbf{0}$: all spin is attributable to the pure component

FIG. 1. Spin-vector geometry for $n = 3$, shown in the plane spanned by Z_O and the transverse projection of the relevant spin vectors. Blue: total spin \mathbf{n} ; green: pure-component contribution $P_1 \mathbf{n}_p$; dashed red: excess spin δ ; dashed orange and purple: transverse and axial excess components. Panel (a) represents a regular state, for which $\delta = \mathbf{0}$; the blue and green vectors are slightly displaced for visibility although they coincide mathematically. Panel (b) represents a generic nonregular state with both transverse and axial excess. Panel (c) represents a nonregular state with purely axial excess, $\delta_{NR} = \mathbf{0}$ but $\delta = \delta_R \neq \mathbf{0}$, where the transverse spin of the full state is entirely supplied by the dominant pure component. In a nondegenerate IRB the drawing is a projection rather than a rotation of the intrinsic axes; an azimuthal orientation of δ_{NR} within the $X_O Y_O$ plane may also be present.

(panel (a)). For a general nonregular state, $\mathbf{n} \not\parallel Z_O$ and the excess has both components, $\delta_{NR} \neq \mathbf{0}$ and $\delta_R \neq \mathbf{0}$ (panel (b)). A more subtle case arises when $\mathbf{n} \not\parallel Z_O$ but $\delta_{NR} = \mathbf{0}$ and $\delta_3 \neq 0$ (panel (c)). This occurs when the dominant axis of ρ_d , transported into the IRB of ρ , becomes parallel to Z_O (angle $\psi = 0$ in the parametrization of Proposition 2 below): the discriminant's imaginary content is then aligned with Z_O in the full-state IRB, so the pure component carries all of the transverse spin, $n_i = P_1 n_{p,i}$ for $i = 1, 2$. The state is nonregular despite the zero transverse excess, and $P_{Ng}^{(3)} = 2|\delta_3| > 0$. This case shows that the regularity criterion is $\delta = \mathbf{0}$ and not $\delta_{NR} = \mathbf{0}$. The δ_{NR}/δ_R decomposition reflects the geometry of the two IRBs, not two separate sources of nonregularity. The perfect nonregular state corresponds to purely transverse excess; intermediate orientations yield mixed decompositions; and the limiting orientation $\psi = 0$ is that of minimal transverse excess at fixed nonregularity. In every case $P_{Ng}^{(3)} = 2|\delta|$ captures the full magnitude.

D. Axial-transverse decomposition of the excess spin

Proposition 2. *In three dimensions,*

$$|\delta_{NR}| = \frac{(P_2 - P_1) |\sin 2\chi|}{2} \sin \psi, \quad (36)$$

$$|\delta_3| = \frac{(P_2 - P_1) |\sin 2\chi|}{2} \cos \psi, \quad (37)$$

where χ is the ellipticity angle of the discriminant's dominant eigenvector, and $\psi \in [0, \pi/2]$ is the polar angle, in the IRB of ρ , between the dominant axis of ρ_d (transported from the IRB of ρ_d into that of ρ) and Z_O . The

ratio $|\delta_{NR}|/|\delta_3| = \tan \psi$ is therefore fixed by the relative axial-transverse orientation of the two intrinsic frames. The polar angle ψ controls only the axial-transverse partition of the excess; the orientation of δ_{NR} within the $X_O Y_O$ plane is governed by an independent azimuthal angle, except in degenerate or symmetric cases where it is absorbed into residual orthogonal freedom. At fixed discriminant weight and fixed orientation (ψ , azimuth), the scalar magnitude of nonregularity is governed by the single amplitude parameter χ .

Proof. In the IRB of ρ_d the discriminant's spin reads $\mathbf{n}_d^{(d)} = \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\chi \hat{\mathbf{e}}_1$ [3]. Real-orthogonal Frobenius-norm invariance gives $|\mathbf{n}_d| = \frac{1}{2} |\sin 2\chi|$ in any real-orthogonal frame, so in the IRB of ρ one can write $\mathbf{n}_d = \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\chi \hat{\mathbf{v}}$, where $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ is the unit vector that the dominant axis of ρ_d defines in the IRB of ρ (modulo the residual orthogonal freedom inside any degenerate subspace of $\text{Re } \rho$). Letting $\psi \in [0, \pi/2]$ denote the angle between $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ and Z_O , the excess spin reads

$$\delta = (P_2 - P_1) \mathbf{n}_d = \frac{(P_2 - P_1) \sin 2\chi}{2} \hat{\mathbf{v}}. \quad (38)$$

Projection onto the $X_O Y_O$ plane (transverse) and the Z_O axis (axial) yields Eqs. (36) and (37), respectively. \square

The boundary $\psi = \pi/2$, attained in particular by the perfect nonregular state ($P_2 - P_1 = 1$ and $\chi = \pi/4$), gives $\delta_3 = 0$: excess entirely transverse. The boundary $\psi = 0$ (Fig. 1c) gives $|\delta_{NR}| = 0$: excess entirely axial. Between these extremes $P_{Ng}^{(3)} = 2|\delta|$ measures the full excess magnitude, while the vector direction records the orientation parameter ψ .

E. Vector discrimination of nonregular states

The vector measure $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ carries information that the scalar measure does not. Two nonregular states with the same $P_{Ng}^{(3)}$ but different orientations of $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ in the IRB are structurally distinct. The orientation is encoded by the angle ψ introduced in Proposition 2, which acts as a second independent parameter beyond the magnitude $|\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}|$. Two physically meaningful extreme configurations follow: $\psi = \pi/2$, for which $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ lies in the dominant transverse plane and the excess cohesion is purely non-axial, as in the perfect nonregular state; and $\psi = 0$, for which $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ is aligned with the dominant axis and all transverse spin originates from the pure component, as in Fig. 1(c). The scalar measure is blind to this distinction because it discards the direction of δ upon taking its norm. In three dimensions, therefore, the natural geometric object characterizing nonregularity is the vector measure (32), with the scalar measure recovered as its norm.

This refinement is specific to $n = 3$. For $n \geq 4$ the antisymmetric matrix $\text{Im}(\rho_d)$ no longer admits a single-vector representation: it lives in $\Lambda^2 \mathbb{R}^n \cong \mathfrak{so}(n)$, the space

of real bivectors, of dimension $n(n-1)/2$. Only in $n=3$ does this dimension equal three, so that Hodge duality identifies a bivector with an axial vector. For $n \geq 4$ the geometric information is therefore distributed across several independent matrix entries, and the appropriate object is the full antisymmetric matrix $\text{Im}(\rho_d)$ rather than a single vector.

F. Connection to the geometry of orthogonal eigenstate sets

The vector measure $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ admits a transparent geometric interpretation in terms of the spatial arrangement of the polarization ellipses of the spectral eigenstates of ρ , analyzed in detail in Ref. [10]. The discriminant component ρ_d of the discriminating decomposition is the equiprobable mixture of the two dominant eigenstates,

$$\rho_d = \frac{1}{2}(\hat{u}_1\hat{u}_1^\dagger + \hat{u}_2\hat{u}_2^\dagger), \quad (39)$$

so the geometric content of ρ_d is determined entirely by the relative configuration of the pair (\hat{u}_1, \hat{u}_2) . Three structural facts about any orthonormal set $\{\hat{u}_1, \hat{u}_2, \hat{u}_3\}$ of three-dimensional Jones eigenvectors [10] are pertinent here. First, the spin vectors of the eigenstates sum to zero, $\sum_k \mathbf{n}_k = \mathbf{0}$, since $\sum_k \hat{u}_k\hat{u}_k^\dagger = I$ and the imaginary part of the identity vanishes; the three eigenstate spins are therefore coplanar. Second, the polarization-ellipse planes of \hat{u}_2 and \hat{u}_3 share a common overall azimuth in the IRB of \hat{u}_1 . Third, the regularity of ρ is determined by the relative orientation of the polarization-ellipse planes of \hat{u}_1 and \hat{u}_2 . These three facts, taken together, combine into the following quantitative statement: $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ is, up to the discriminant weight $w = P_2 - P_1$, a monotone function of the geometric departure from coplanarity between the polarization-ellipse planes of \hat{u}_1 and \hat{u}_2 . Coplanarity gives $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)} = \mathbf{0}$; the maximally non-coplanar configuration, in which one ellipse degenerates to a line orthogonal to the plane of a circle (the structure imposed by Theorem 1 in $n=3$), gives $|\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}| = 1$. The continuum in between is parametrized by the ellipticity angle χ of Proposition 2. The vector measure $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ thus quantifies, in a single intrinsic vector, the geometric content that Ref. [10] characterized qualitatively.

G. Examples

The framework is now illustrated with two examples that span the relevant phenomenology: a one-parameter family of states that displays the IRB as a strictly finer descriptor than the spectrum, and an explicit construction taken from Ref. [10] that connects the geometric measure to a previously analyzed three-dimensional configuration.

a. Example 1: states unitarily equivalent but resolved by the IRB. Consider the family

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(\chi) &= \frac{1}{2}|0\rangle\langle 0| + \frac{1}{2}|\psi_\chi\rangle\langle\psi_\chi|, \\ |\psi_\chi\rangle &= \cos\chi|1\rangle + i\sin\chi|2\rangle, \quad \chi \in [0, \pi/4]. \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

The basis $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle, |2\rangle\}$ is treated as a fixed real basis selected by the physical context: in the polarization realization, the Cartesian axes of the field; in the qutrit realization, an externally distinguished computational basis (for instance the magnetic-sublevel basis of a spin-1 system, or the energy eigenbasis of a real Hamiltonian). The eigenvalues of $\rho(\chi)$ are $(1/2, 1/2, 0)$ for every χ in the stated range, so all spectrum-derived quantities — purity $\text{tr}\rho^2$, von Neumann entropy, indices of purity P_1, P_2 — are independent of χ . Any quantity invariant under arbitrary unitary conjugation $\rho \mapsto V\rho V^\dagger$ is therefore constant across the family.

The IRB analysis resolves the family completely. The IRB is determined by $\text{Re}\rho$ in the represented density matrix: in the chosen real basis $\text{Re}\rho(\chi)$ is already diagonal, so the IRB coincides with the basis itself. (The construction is real-orthogonal intrinsic, not unitary invariant: a complex unitary change of representation would generally redistribute imaginary content between basis phases and matrix entries and would alter the IRB accordingly.) The intrinsic populations are

$$a_1 = \frac{1}{2}, \quad a_2 = \frac{1+\cos 2\chi}{4}, \quad a_3 = \frac{1-\cos 2\chi}{4}, \quad (41)$$

and the only nonvanishing off-diagonal entry of $\text{Im}\rho(\chi)$ is $|N_{23}| = (\sin 2\chi)/4$. The eigenvalues $(1/2, 1/2, 0)$ give the indices of purity $P_1 = \lambda_1 - \lambda_2 = 0$ and $P_2 = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 - 2\lambda_3 = 1$, hence the discriminant weight is $w = P_2 - P_1 = 1$ and the family is itself a one-parameter family of normalized discriminants, $\rho(\chi) = \rho_d$, with no pure-state or isotropic component. The cohesion is $\|\text{Im}\rho(\chi)\|_F = |\sin 2\chi|/(2\sqrt{2})$, monotone in χ , vanishing at $\chi = 0$ (a regular discriminant with two real eigenvectors in the $|1\rangle, |2\rangle$ plane) and reaching the universal three-dimensional bound $N_3 = 1/(2\sqrt{2})$ at $\chi = \pi/4$ (the perfect nonregular state). The scalar geometric measure and the original scalar degree admit closed forms

$$P_{Ng}^{(3)}(\chi) = \sin 2\chi, \quad P_N(\chi) = 1 - \cos 2\chi, \quad (42)$$

and satisfy the quarter-circle identity $(P_{Ng}^{(3)})^2 + (P_N - w)^2 = w^2 = 1$ identically in χ . Spectral and entropic descriptors — being constant on the family — cannot resolve the family; the IRB-based descriptors do, and trace the regular-to-perfect-nonregular interpolation explicitly.

The interpretation is dual. In polarimetric terms, $\rho(\chi)$ is a discriminating component built from a linear state along $|0\rangle$ and an elliptic state of ellipticity χ in the plane $\{|1\rangle, |2\rangle\}$. In qutrit terms, $\rho(\chi)$ is a maximally mixed state on the two-dimensional support spanned by $|0\rangle$ and a relative-phase superposition of $|1\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$, with phase $\pi/2$ between them at $\chi = \pi/4$ and a real superposition at $\chi = 0$. The mathematical content is the same; only the operational interpretation of the basis changes.

b. Example 2: the incoherent mixture of two circular states in orthogonal planes. We revisit the construction analyzed in Ref. [10]: the equal-weight incoherent mixture of two right-circularly-polarized states whose polarization circles lie in mutually orthogonal planes,

$$\rho = \frac{1}{2}\rho_{cx} + \frac{1}{2}\rho_{cy} = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & i \\ 0 & 1 & i \\ -i & -i & 2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (43)$$

Direct computation yields the spectral weights $\hat{\lambda}_{1,2,3} = (3/4, 1/4, 0)$, the indices of purity $(P_1, P_2) = (1/2, 1)$, and the discriminant weight $w = P_2 - P_1 = 1/2$. The Frobenius norm of the imaginary part of the normalized discriminant is $\|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F = 1/3$, and the smallest intrinsic population of ρ_d is $\hat{m}_{d3} = 1/6$. Substituting in Eqs. (31) and (13),

$$P_{Ng}^{(3)} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \approx 0.471, \quad P_N = \frac{1}{3} \approx 0.333, \quad (44)$$

and the quarter-circle identity is satisfied: $(P_{Ng}^{(3)})^2 + (P_N - w)^2 = 2/9 + 1/36 = 1/4 = w^2$. The state is therefore manifestly nonregular but not maximally so. The geometric origin is transparent: although the two circular components used to build ρ are perpendicular and intuitively orthogonal, the spectral eigenstates of the mixture have polarization ellipses that are non-coplanar and of intermediate ellipticity $\chi_1 = \arctan(1/\sqrt{2}) \approx 35.26^\circ$ [10], producing the residual imaginary cohesion measured by $P_{Ng}^{(3)}$. Read as a qutrit, ρ is the equal mixture of two spin-1 states whose circular-polarization planes are orthogonal in the chosen real basis; the same numerical values for $P_{Ng}^{(3)}$ and P_N apply. This example shows that nontrivial three-dimensional mixings produce nonregularity automatically, and that the geometric measure provides a finite, computable, well-defined value for it.

VI. COMPARISON WITH THE ORIGINAL SCALAR DEGREE P_N

A. Common structural properties

Both $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ and P_N are bounded in $[0, 1]$, vanish exactly for regular states, and are intrinsic invariants under real orthogonal transformations of the represented density matrix. The discriminating decomposition that supplies ρ_d is unitary covariant and its weights are spectral invariants, but the two nonregularity measures themselves are not unitary spectral invariants. These common properties establish them as equivalent qualitative detectors of nonregularity within the intrinsic real-orthogonal framework.

B. Structural difference: norm versus correlation-asymmetry

Their quantitative content differs. The scalar geometric measure, defined in Eq. (30), captures the total Frobenius norm of the excess cohesion, irrespective of how that cohesion is distributed across intrinsic axis pairs. The original scalar degree P_N captures the correlation-asymmetry structure of the discriminant, as defined in Ref. [1]; in three dimensions it reduces to the particularly simple expression $P_N = 4(P_2 - P_1)\hat{m}_{d3}$. Thus, in $n = 3$ the two scalar quantities are related by the exact quarter-circle identity proved below. In higher dimensions the geometric norm and the full correlation-asymmetry structure carry complementary rather than identical information: the former measures the total amount of excess cohesion, while the latter records how that cohesion contributes to the hierarchy of intrinsic correlation asymmetries.

For $n = 3$, the discriminant's imaginary content is always concentrated in a single pair, as shown in Proposition 2, so both measures reduce to functions of the single parameter χ and are equivalent for fixed $P_2 - P_1$. For $n \geq 4$, the imaginary content can be distributed over multiple non-sharing pairs, and the total Frobenius norm and the smallest eigenvalue of $\text{Re}(\rho_d)$ carry genuinely different information. In this sense P_{Ng} and P_N are complementary for $n \geq 4$: neither determines the other. The full hierarchical structure of this distribution can be organized by a nested family of invariants of the antisymmetric block of the discriminant, a refinement that will be developed separately and that provides the common ancestor of both scalar descriptors.

C. Exact equivalence in three dimensions: the quarter-circle

Theorem 3. For $n = 3$ and fixed $P_2 - P_1 > 0$ (using $w = P_2 - P_1$ as shorthand),

$$(P_{Ng}^{(3)})^2 + (P_N - w)^2 = w^2. \quad (45)$$

The pair $(P_{Ng}^{(3)}, P_N)$ traces a quarter-circle arc of radius $P_2 - P_1$ from $(0, 0)$ (regular) to $(P_2 - P_1, P_2 - P_1)$ (perfect nonregular) as χ ranges over $[0, \pi/4]$.

Proof. In three dimensions, $P_N(\rho_d) = 4\hat{m}_{d3}$ with $\hat{m}_{d3} = a_{d,3}$, the smallest intrinsic population of ρ_d . For a discriminating state parametrized by the ellipticity angle $\chi \in [0, \pi/4]$ of its canonical eigenstates, its intrinsic populations may be written as

$$a_{d,1} = \frac{1}{2}, \quad a_{d,2} = \frac{1 + \cos 2\chi}{4}, \quad a_{d,3} = \frac{1 - \cos 2\chi}{4}, \quad (46)$$

so that the ordering $a_{d,1} \geq a_{d,2} \geq a_{d,3}$ is automatic on $\chi \in [0, \pi/4]$. The active intrinsic coherence is $|N_{d,23}| =$

$(\sin 2\chi)/4$ (see [2, 3]). Therefore

$$P_N = 4w \hat{m}_{d3} = w(1 - \cos 2\chi). \quad (47)$$

Moreover $\|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F = (\sin 2\chi)/(2\sqrt{2})$, and hence $P_{Ng}^{(3)} = w \sin 2\chi$. Setting $t = \cos 2\chi \in [0, 1]$ gives $P_N = w(1 - t)$ and $P_{Ng}^{(3)} = w\sqrt{1 - t^2}$, so $(P_{Ng}^{(3)})^2 + (P_N - w)^2 = w^2(1 - t^2) + w^2 t^2 = w^2$. \square

Corollary 1. *The explicit conversions are*

$$P_{Ng}^{(3)} = \sqrt{P_N(2(P_2 - P_1) - P_N)}, \quad (48)$$

$$P_N = (P_2 - P_1) \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{P_{Ng}^{(3)}}{P_2 - P_1} \right)^2} \right]. \quad (49)$$

For fixed $P_2 - P_1$, both measures are strictly monotone in each other and induce the same ordering on states.

VII. DISCUSSION

A. Quantum-mechanical interpretation

The construction is intended to be read as a statement about density matrices, not merely about optical polarization matrices. In a finite-dimensional quantum system, the spectrum of ρ fixes mixedness but not the resolved arrangement of populations and imaginary coherences in a represented matrix. The IRB supplies a canonical real frame for that arrangement: its PPCS are the states that diagonalize $S = \text{Re } \rho$, while $N = \text{Im } \rho_O$ contains the preserved cohesion between those states. The nonregularity measure then asks a sharply defined question: how much of the intrinsic cohesion remains after subtracting the portion carried by the dominant pure component of the discriminating decomposition?

This makes $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ complementary to eigenvalue-based purity, entropy, and generalized Bloch-vector coordinates. It is also distinct from resource-theoretic coherence relative to an externally prescribed incoherent basis. Here the resolving basis is produced by the density matrix itself. Sensitivity to the choice of representation is the very feature that makes $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ a well-defined intrinsic physical functional of the represented density matrix: it detects population-coherence structure that any spectral or unitary-averaged label necessarily erases.

A further conceptual distinction is worth emphasizing. Global purity-like descriptors (the degree of purity P_{3D} , the indices of purity P_1, P_2 , the entropy) quantify how much structure ρ carries in absolute terms. They are global in the sense that they evaluate the entire state without reference to any specific component of its decomposition. The geometric measure $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$, by contrast, is a structural or relative descriptor: it quantifies the cohesion of ρ that cannot be attributed to its

dominant pure component. The decomposition $\text{Im } \rho = P_1 \text{Im } \rho_p + (P_{n-1} - P_1) \text{Im } \rho_d$ partitions the imaginary content into a piece explained by the rank-one projector onto \hat{u}_1 and a piece carried by ρ_d ; $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ measures the latter. This places it conceptually closer to residual descriptors of quantum information theory (such as quantum discord, which quantifies correlations not attributable to a classical reference) than to direct coherence quantifiers. The two roles are complementary rather than substitutive: a global descriptor reports how much there is, while a structural descriptor reports what is left after a natural piece has been subtracted.

B. Computational and experimental aspects

The scalar measure $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ and the vector measure $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ require, from the spectral decomposition of ρ , only the first two eigenvalues (through $P_1 = \lambda_1 - \lambda_2$), the smallest eigenvalue (through $P_{n-1} - P_1$), and the dominant eigenvector \hat{u}_1 . The full discriminating decomposition can be bypassed in the calculation of the excess-cohesion norm, because Eq. (28) expresses it directly in terms of ρ and ρ_p . This is advantageous in numerical settings, for instance in the direct diagonalization of correlation matrices or in simulations of multilevel density matrices where constructing ρ_d explicitly would require resolving the full spectrum.

In the polarization realization, ρ is the field-correlation matrix and is accessible by the same Stokes-like reconstructions used in three-dimensional polarimetry [19–21]; both $P_{Ng}^{(3)}$ and $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ are therefore experimentally measurable in evanescent-wave and tightly focused-beam settings, where genuinely three-dimensional polarization states have been characterized.

C. Qutrits and three-component classical polarization

The three-dimensional case, where the vector formulation applies, has two distinct physical realizations. In the quantum regime, $n = 3$ corresponds to qutrits, the first nontrivial qudits beyond qubits, and to generic three-level systems. For such states, ρ is the density matrix of the three-state quantum system, and the vector measure provides a concrete geometric characterization of intrinsic imaginary cohesion not attributable to the dominant eigenstate. In the classical regime, $n = 3$ corresponds to the polarization state of a three-component electromagnetic field, where ρ is the Hermitian polarization matrix of the field and \mathbf{n} is the dimensionless polarimetric spin vector dual to its antisymmetric block [11, 14, 15]; this vector is proportional to the electric spin angular momentum density for monochromatic light, but for general random polychromatic light the two vectors do not in general coincide in direction [15]. The vector mea-

sure $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ quantifies the excess spin associated with the discriminant in this polarimetric sense.

Genuine three-dimensional electromagnetic fields occur in near-field optics, in evanescent waves arising in total internal reflection [22], and in tightly focused beams where the longitudinal component cannot be neglected [14]. In these settings the three-dimensional character is intrinsic. The normalization $\mathcal{N}_3 = 1/(2\sqrt{2})$ is therefore not a matter of convention: adopting the $n \geq 4$ normalization in a genuinely three-dimensional system would incorrectly bound the scalar measure at $1/\sqrt{2} < 1$.

The qutrit visualization developed by Kurzynski et al. [17] provides a complementary perspective. Their three-dimensional ellipsoid is built from the same eigen-decomposition of $\text{Re } \rho$ that defines the IRB, and their Bloch-like vector coincides — up to a factor of two — with the spin vector \mathbf{n} used here. In that representation, regularity corresponds to alignment of the Bloch-like vector with the principal axis of the ellipsoid associated with the dominant eigenvalue of $\hat{T} = I - 2 \text{Re } \rho$, and the geometric measure $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ quantifies the angular deviation from that alignment, weighted by the discriminant amplitude. The polarization density object of Ref. [11] provides the analogous picture in the optical-polarization realization, with the spin density vector $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_O$ playing the role of $\mathbf{n}/2$. In both pictures, what was already a transparent geometric criterion (whether the spin/Bloch vector is aligned with a specific principal axis of the intrinsic ellipsoid) now acquires a quantitative companion: $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ measures the misalignment, not merely diagnoses it.

D. Information visible only in the IRB formulation

The value of the IRB formulation is particularly clear in three dimensions. The spectral and characteristic decompositions of a 3×3 density matrix involve orthonormal complex vectors. In polarization language these are three-dimensional Jones vectors, and their mathematical orthogonality does not generally mean that the planes of the corresponding polarization ellipses are mutually orthogonal [10]. The geometry of those orthogonal sets contains physical information that is not apparent from the eigenvalues and is not captured by a scalar weight alone. The same statement has a qutrit counterpart: orthogonality in Hilbert space does not by itself reveal how the imaginary coherences are distributed among the intrinsic real planes.

This observation explains why P_{Ng} is useful even when the original scalar degree P_N is already available. The scalar P_N detects the strength of nonregularity through the correlation-asymmetry structure of the discriminant. The scalar P_{Ng} measures the norm of the excess cohesion.

In three dimensions, however, the vector $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ also gives the direction of that excess spin in the IRB. Thus two states can agree in scalar nonregularity while differing in the orientation of the excess cohesion. Such differences

are physically meaningful: in polarization they correspond to different arrangements of spin and polarization-ellipse geometry; in qutrits they correspond to different allocations of phase-oriented coherence among the intrinsic two-level sectors.

The model of orthogonal three-dimensional polarization states provides a useful illustration. The characteristic middle component is determined by a pair of orthonormal states, and its regularity depends on their geometric relation [10]. A purely scalar description can identify whether the state is regular or nonregular and can quantify the amount of nonregularity. The vector geometric description adds the missing information: it identifies the intrinsic direction of the cohesion that makes the discriminant complex. In this sense certain physical properties only emerge once the density matrix is viewed through the IRB and the excess cohesion is treated as a geometric object.

E. Range of applicability

The IRB construction applies to any density matrix in any chosen representation, regardless of dynamical or symmetry assumptions. Its descriptors quantify representation-intrinsic structural features that are real-orthogonal-invariant. The construction is, however, most informative when the chosen basis is itself physically distinguished. Three settings in which this occurs are worth mentioning explicitly. First, in three-component polarization, the Cartesian field basis is selected by the spatial geometry of the experimental setup, and the IRB descriptors then have direct geometric meaning as intrinsic Stokes parameters and excess spin [11, 14]. Second, in time-reversal-symmetric quantum systems, when the chosen basis realizes time reversal as complex conjugation, the cohesion $\|N\|_F$ is literally a measure of T -violation: T -invariant states correspond exactly to $\text{Im } \rho = 0$, and a positive cohesion quantifies the departure from the T -invariant subspace. Third, in systems with a real Hamiltonian, $[H, T] = 0$ in the chosen basis implies that the T -invariant subspace is dynamically preserved by unitary evolution, although neither the cohesion nor the geometric measures are constants of motion in general (the global unitary group is broader than the real-orthogonal subgroup that fixes the IRB descriptors). In settings where no preferred real basis exists, the IRB is still well-defined but its descriptors acquire physical content only after such a basis is specified by the application.

F. The dimensional transition

The transition from $n = 3$ to $n \geq 4$ is a structural transition in the character of perfect nonregularity: from a circular-plus-linear object to a doubly-coherent two-sector object. The normalization constant increases from

$\mathcal{N}_3 = 1/(2\sqrt{2})$ to $\mathcal{N}_{n \geq 4} = 1/2 = \sqrt{2}\mathcal{N}_3$, reflecting the enhanced cohesion capacity available when a second mutually orthogonal maximally coherent sector can be accommodated. The special character of $n = 3$ is not accidental: it is the minimal dimension where the discriminant component exists and can be complex, and this minimality forces the perfect nonregular state to contain a real direction. From $n = 4$ onward, irrespective of parity, the conjugate-orthogonal two-sector configuration becomes available and is the universal maximizer.

G. The quarter-circle: geometric unification for $n = 3$

For $n = 3$, the quarter-circle (45) provides a complete geometric unification of the two scalar measures at fixed discriminant weight $w = P_2 - P_1$: the pair $(P_{Ng}^{(3)}, P_N)$ traces an arc of radius w in the first quadrant, parametrized by $\theta = 2\chi \in [0, \pi/2]$. The endpoints correspond to $\theta = 0$ (regular state, $P_{Ng} = P_N = 0$) and $\theta = \pi/2$ (perfect nonregular state, $P_{Ng} = P_N = w$). The scalar measures are therefore equivalent for the purpose of ordering nonregularity at fixed w , but the vector measure $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)}$ adds the angle ψ , which distinguishes states lying on the same quarter-circle but carrying excess spin in different intrinsic directions.

For $n \geq 4$, no analogous single-parameter vector reduction exists: the imaginary cohesion can be distributed over multiple intrinsic pairs, and the scalar norm does not by itself encode the complete hierarchy of correlation-asymmetry descriptors.

H. Hierarchical refinement in higher dimensions

The scalar measure $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ for $n \geq 4$ captures the global Frobenius norm of the excess cohesion, but a single scalar cannot record how that cohesion is distributed across principal coherence pairs of the discriminant. Two structurally inequivalent discriminating configurations in dimension four illustrate this. The doubly-coherent state has two simultaneously saturating Youla values and realizes $\|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F = \mathcal{N}_4$. A single-pair dominated configuration has one saturating Youla value and a second one that contributes partially; it sits strictly below \mathcal{N}_4 unless the second pair also saturates, so it does not realize the maximum discriminant cohesion. Both configurations may nevertheless produce equal values of the original scalar degree P_N , which records the correlation-asymmetry structure rather than the total Frobenius norm. A hierarchical resolution of this kind of degeneracy is possible through a nested family of dimensionless invariants attached to the skew-singular values of a normalized antisymmetric tensor associated with the discriminant; the construction will be reported separately. In dimension three, the hierarchical refinement reduces

to the magnitude of the metaspin vector and is therefore equivalent to the vector formulation (32) up to Hodge duality. From dimension four onward, the hierarchical and the present scalar formulations carry genuinely different content: the former resolves the distribution of excess cohesion across principal pairs, while $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ records the total magnitude. The two formulations are therefore complementary, and together they supply, for any finite dimension, both the global amount of nonregularity and the structural pattern through which it is realized.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

The article has developed two connected results. The first is a clarified interpretation of the intrinsic reference basis of a density matrix. For any represented Hermitian density matrix $\rho = S + iT$, the real symmetric part S defines a real orthonormal basis through its principal axes. The states of this basis have been named principal population-coherence states, or PPCS. They form the intrinsic reference basis (IRB) and are also intrinsic resolving states: they diagonalize and order the population-bearing part while preserving the Frobenius weight of the imaginary antisymmetric part. Thus the IRB is a cohesion-preserving population-coherence representation. It does not diagonalize ρ completely and does not erase coherence; instead, it displays the matrix as $\rho_O = A + iN$, where A contains the intrinsic populations and N contains the preserved intrinsic cohesion.

The second result is the geometric formulation of nonregularity. Regularity is the limiting case in which the discriminant component of the discriminating decomposition is real. Nonregularity is therefore the presence of imaginary cohesion in the discriminant. The scalar geometric measure $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$, defined in Eq. (30), is the normalized Frobenius norm of the excess cohesion $\text{Im}(\rho) - P_1 \text{Im}(\rho_p)$. It is bounded in $[0, 1]$, vanishes exactly for regular states, equals unity at the perfect nonregular state of the corresponding dimension, and is computable directly from ρ and the dominant pure component.

The normalization of $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ is fixed by the dimensional structure of maximally nonregular discriminants. Theorem 1 shows that the maximum is $\mathcal{N}_3 = 1/(2\sqrt{2})$ for $n = 3$ and $\mathcal{N}_{n \geq 4} = 1/2$ for all higher dimensions. This is a genuine structural transition. In three dimensions the support of the discriminant must share a real direction with its conjugate, leading to the circular-plus-linear perfect nonregular state. From four dimensions onward a conjugate-orthogonal support is possible, and the perfect nonregular state becomes a doubly-coherent two-sector mixture.

In three dimensions, relevant both to qutrits and to three-component polarization matrices, the excess cohesion is dual to an excess spin vector. The vector measure $\mathbf{P}_{Ng}^{(3)} = 2(\mathbf{n} - P_1 \mathbf{n}_p)$ refines the scalar measure by retaining the intrinsic direction of the nonregular contribution. This exposes physical information that the original scalar

degree P_N does not display by itself. The quarter-circle identity, $(P_{Ng}^{(3)})^2 + [P_N - (P_2 - P_1)]^2 = (P_2 - P_1)^2$, shows that $P_{Ng}^{(3)}$ and P_N are scalar-equivalent at fixed discriminant weight, while the vector formulation adds the geometrical orientation of the excess cohesion.

Taken together, the IRB and P_{Ng} provide a self-consistent framework for resolving and quantifying non-regularity across finite dimensions. The construction is applicable to qutrits and higher-dimensional qudits, to three-level quantum systems, to three-component classical polarization fields in near-field and evanescent-wave settings, and more broadly to any represented density matrix for which the separation between intrinsic popula-

tions and imaginary cohesion is physically or structurally relevant.

STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

Funding. The author did not receive support from any organization for the submitted work.

Competing interests. The author has no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Data availability. No new data were generated or analyzed in support of this research.

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- [1] J. J. Gil, Sources of asymmetry and the concept of nonregularity of n -dimensional density matrices, *Symmetry* **12**, 1002 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym12061002>.
- [2] J. J. Gil, A. Norrman, A. T. Friberg, and T. Setälä, Discriminating states of polarization, *Photonics* **10**, 1050 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/photonics10091050>.
- [3] J. J. Gil, A. Norrman, A. T. Friberg, and T. Setälä, Non-regularity of three-dimensional polarization states, *Opt. Lett.* **43**, 4611–4614 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1364/OL.43.004611>.
- [4] U. Fano, Description of states in quantum mechanics by density matrix and operator techniques, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **29**, 74–93 (1957), <https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.29.74>.
- [5] M. S. Byrd and N. Khaneja, Characterization of the positivity of the density matrix in terms of the coherence vector representation, *Phys. Rev. A* **68**, 062322 (2003), <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.68.062322>.
- [6] G. Kimura, The Bloch vector for N -level systems, *Phys. Lett. A* **314**, 339–349 (2003), [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0375-9601\(03\)00941-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0375-9601(03)00941-1).
- [7] I. Bengtsson and K. Życzkowski, *Geometry of Quantum States: An Introduction to Quantum Entanglement*, 2nd ed. (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2017).
- [8] T. Baumgratz, M. Cramer, and M. B. Plenio, Quantifying coherence, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **113**, 140401 (2014), <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.113.140401>.
- [9] A. Streltsov, G. Adesso, and M. B. Plenio, Colloquium: Quantum coherence as a resource, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **89**, 041003 (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.89.041003>.
- [10] J. J. Gil, I. San José, A. Norrman, A. T. Friberg, and T. Setälä, Sets of orthogonal three-dimensional polarization states and their physical interpretation, *Phys. Rev. A* **100**, 033824 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.100.033824>.
- [11] J. J. Gil, Geometric interpretation and general classification of three-dimensional polarization states through the intrinsic Stokes parameters, *Photonics* **8**, 315 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.3390/photonics8080315>.
- [12] J. J. Gil, Interpretation of the coherency matrix for three-dimensional polarization states, *Phys. Rev. A* **90**, 043858 (2014), <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.90.043858>.
- [13] M. R. Dennis, Geometric interpretation of the three-dimensional coherence matrix for nonparaxial polarization, *J. Opt. A: Pure Appl. Opt.* **6**, S26–S31 (2004), <https://doi.org/10.1088/1464-4258/6/3/005>.
- [14] J. J. Gil, A. Norrman, A. T. Friberg, and T. Setälä, Effect of polarimetric nonregularity on the spin of three-dimensional polarization states, *New J. Phys.* **23**, 063059 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1088/1367-2630/abd9e5>.
- [15] J. J. Gil, A. Norrman, A. T. Friberg, and T. Setälä, Spin of random stationary light, *Phys. Rev. A* **107**, 053518 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.107.053518>.
- [16] J. J. Gil, A. Norrman, A. T. Friberg, and T. Setälä, Descriptors of dimensionality for $n \times n$ density matrices, *Eur. Phys. J. Plus* **138**, 476 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjp/s13360-023-04109-8>.
- [17] P. Kurzynski, A. Kolodziejcki, W. Laskowski, and M. Markiewicz, Three-dimensional visualization of a qutrit, *Phys. Rev. A* **93**, 062126 (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.93.062126>.
- [18] I. San José and J. J. Gil, Invariant indices of polarimetric purity: Generalized indices of purity for $n \times n$ covariance matrices, *Opt. Commun.* **284**, 38–47 (2011), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optcom.2010.08.077>.
- [19] T. Setälä, A. Shevchenko, M. Kaivola, and A. T. Friberg, Degree of polarization for optical near fields, *Phys. Rev. E* **66**, 016615 (2002), <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.66.016615>.
- [20] T. Setälä, M. Kaivola, and A. T. Friberg, Degree of polarization in near fields of thermal sources: Effects of surface waves, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **88**, 123902 (2002), <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.88.123902>.
- [21] Y. Chen, F. Wang, Z. Dong, Y. Cai, A. Norrman, J. J. Gil, A. T. Friberg, and T. Setälä, Polarimetric dimension and nonregularity of tightly focused light beams, *Phys. Rev. A* **101**, 053825 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.101.053825>.
- [22] A. Norrman, J. J. Gil, A. T. Friberg, and T. Setälä, Polarimetric nonregularity of evanescent waves, *Opt. Lett.* **44**, 215–218 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1364/OL.44.000215>.